

A perspective on Fatigue Performance of Rail Profiles under Shuttle Loads

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ABSTRACT

Cold roll forming is a continuous process aiming a progressive bending of sheet steel using stations with rotating rolls, without changing material thickness [1]. Racking systems used today in logistic industries are normally made of thin-walled cold formed steel members. Cold roll forming processes introduce residual stresses in steel components and when combined with service loading stresses (e.g. due to the passage of shuttles in racking systems), these stresses may change the resulting stress range or average, affecting fatigue life of these components. FASTCOLD project purpose is to develop fatigue design rules for cold formed steel members. Design rules already exist for hot-rolled steel details in EN1993-1-9 [2]. However, for cold formed steel sections, they are missing on a European level (EN1993-1-9: Design of steel structures - Part 1-9: Fatigue does not present fatigue design rules or classification of cold-formed thin-walled details) [2]. Due to the lack of these fatigue design rules for cold rolled formed steel members, this paper aims at analysing the stresses induced by roll forming and propose a setup for testing representative rail profiles under fatigue loadings that could arise from shuttle moving loads.

Numerical simulations of cold-formed steel sections have been performed using COPRA FEA code. Relevant residual stresses have been computed and fatigue analysis performed for applied external loads. More importantly, an evaluation of residual stresses distribution across the thickness and along the surface of the strip width was performed [3]. The development and design of the simulation models (specification of machine parameters, rolls design, flower patten, mesh definition, etc.) and the numerical simulation were performed using COPRA® FEA RF finite element software. The roll forming numerical simulations were performed for a Z-section profile, in order to analyse the three-dimensional effects of this manufacturing process in this structure, as well as the residual stresses generated (see Fig. 1). Afterwards, a local stress-based approach was used to estimate fatigue life of these components when subjected to cyclic loading. The stress range calculated incorporated the stresses after the roll forming process and the stresses induced by external cyclic loading. A comparison of the maximum load that can be applied in order to achieve a fatigue endurance limit (according to [2], the limit is established for 5 million cycles) was performed (see Fig. 2). Numerical results showed that residual stresses across the thickness displayed some deviations between 2D theoretical solution (press-brake) and 3D roll-forming [3], due to the existence of three-dimensional effects that cannot be neglected (the bending occurs gradually, which can lead to defects such as edge waviness, bow and twist, depending on the design of the process and rolls). Fig. 1 reveals the smaller differences between the theoretical solution and the through the thickness residual stresses distribution of the Z-section profile. Fig. 2 shows the prediction of the S-N curves using local approaches to fatigue. Local stresses result from the superposition of residual stresses from cold-roll forming and the external loads, representative of shuttle loads. In addition to the numerical simulations, an experimental

setup has been developed and the first preliminary tests were performed within FASTCOLD project (see Fig. 3). Different load actuators and boundary conditions have been tested for a successful fatigue test.

Fig. 1. Cold-roll forming of Z-Rail section simulation and analysis of thru thickness residual stresses.

Fig. 2. Z-rail fatigue simulation using local approaches to fatigue with superimposed residual and external load stresses.

Fig. 3. Experimental setup for fatigue testing of Z-rail profiles.

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